

Editorial

Big Data Concept, Analytics and Hadoop Technology: A Systematic Survey

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Big Data Concept, Analytics and Hadoop Technology: A Systematic Survey

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Abstract: This paper provides insight into the concept of big data and big data analytic platforms like Spark and Storm to handle a variety of data coming from various sources like the Internet of Things (IoT) which could pose a challenge in production in the industries. The paper discusses the concept of Industry 4.0 and shows how big data in Industry 4.0 can lead to the growth of the economy and the promotion of business in the industry. The paper presents some challenges faced by big data and proffers solutions to these challenges. Hadoop technology is suggested as one of the methods to address some of the challenges of big data. The components of Hadoop technology such as Hadoop distributed file system (HDES), Map reduce, HBASE, HCatalog, Pig and so on, are discussed alongside their functions. The methodology followed to achieve these objectives stated above is a systematic review of current works of literature and related works.

Key Words: Big Data, Data Analytics, Industry 4.0, Data Challenges, Hadoop Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of Big Data to the industry cannot be overemphasised because of the benefits realised from its analysis. Big Data is the phase that describes the data set with size and type surpassing the capacity of the traditional methods (Komal, 2018; Nagat Mohamed, 2020). Big Data has these attributes: massive volume, great speed, high variety, high accuracy (Komal, 2018) and high complexity. The traditional method differs from data analytics because it is expensive and cannot handle data that are heterogenous and in large volumes (Raheem & Uwanthika, 2019). Data analytics is less expensive and can handle heterogeneous data.

Data analytics is the use of advanced analytical techniques on big data to extract hidden patterns and information to help business organisations to study their business trends, make quick decisions and discharge their duties at a fast rate when compared to the traditional method (Raheem & Uwanthika, 2019). The traditional method can only process data that is in structured form whereas, Big Data analytics can process any form of data. It can be applied to semi-structured, unstructured or no form of data.

Data analytics is a combination of big data and data analysis (Russom, 2011). Big data and data analytics remarkably affect research and technology because decision-makers use the information gained from accumulated data for competitive advantage (Cuzzocrea et al., 2011).

The following sections of the paper will discuss related works, the importance of big data analytics in the industry,

industry 4.0 and its expectations for business organisations, Hadoop and its components, challenges of big data and solutions to big data challenges. The methodology used in this paper was the systematic review of the literature.

II. RELATED WORKS

To meet up with challenges and avoid disruptions in production, Gokalp et al. (2016) built a conceptual framework that supported multiple big data platforms such as Spark, Storm and Flink. Their framework was to handle the variety of data coming from various sources like Internet of Things (IoT) devices which could pose challenges to the acceptance of Big Data analytics in Industry 4.0 (Mishra & Misra, 2017; Shi-Nash & Hardoon, 2017).

Tsai et al. (2015) in their study suggested sampling, data condensation, divide and conquer as methods to reduce the complexity and improve the performance of data analytics. They stated that sampling could be used to accelerate the computational time of data analytics. It should be noted that though sampling speeds up the computational time of data analytics, by it reducing the volume of information, it avoids dreariness in work and the limitation of information may mislead the results. Data condensation is when a small data set replaces a large data set. In this case, one will not have true knowledge of what is happening so one cannot be depended upon to make true decisions concerning customers, production or business trends.

In the review paper and comparative assessment of big data analytics, Komal (2018) identified some of the challenges associated with big data, like data storage issues, data inconsistency, data insecurity and untimeliness, but did not provide solutions that will correct these challenges. The review paper by Elgendy and Elragal (2014) on data analytics discussed some challenges and solutions to big data and data analytics problems. The solutions they provided to solve these challenges were narrowed only to data storage and its management. They developed a non-relational database, not only SQL (NoSQL), for data management and data storage.

III. BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN THE INDUSTRY

Big data analytics is very important and needful in this age where business worlds are in a high competition requiring smart manufacturing, meeting targets, operating at high speed and maintaining high production quality and efficiency (Ajah & Nweke, 2019; Tawalbeh & Saldamli, 2021; Wang et al., 2022).

1. Big data or huge amounts of data are generated in real-time over infrastructures because of advancements in sensor technology and the traditional methods of analysing data cannot manage or handle these data

because of their size.

2. Big data comes in a variety of forms such as structures, semi-structured and unstructured forms and from different sources and sizes that could pose challenges that can prevent the adoption of analytic tools in Industry 4.0. The larger the data the more difficult it is to analyse. Big data analytic tools play an important role in the analysis and mining of a variety of data generated over the internet.
3. Big Data analytic tools perform analysis and mining on huge amounts of data collected from smart sensors to discover patterns and trends to improve business decisions.
4. Big data analytic tools can identify the source(s) of problem production and help the manufacturer to improve productivity while eliminating waste and reducing cost.
5. Control software connected to robots can take inferences made from big data analytic tools to alter settings on equipment and machine without any human intervention.
6. Big data analytics help industries study business trends, make quick decisions and work at a faster rate when compared to the traditional method (Raheem & Uwanthika, 2019).

Elgendy and Elragal (2014) presented the following benefits to be realised in the application of Data analytics on big data.

1. Data analytics enhances Advanced Data Visualisation (ADV) (Russom, 2011), so that information can be consumed effectively to enable decision-makers to analyse data properly (Manyika et al., 2011).
2. Data analytics can enable organisations to invent new products and services, new business ideas and models.
3. Benefits can be realised from big data analytics in customer preference, supply chain intelligence, fraud detection and risk management (Manyika et al., 2011).
4. Big data analytics creates clarity and ensures that appropriate data are easily accessible to the stakeholders on time (Manyika et al., 2011). The main stakeholders that benefit from data analytics are the manufacturers, retailers, government, healthcare system, telecommunication and banking industries.
5. Big data analytics help industries to make more knowledgeable decisions and alert them on time when customers are moving to different products so that prompt actions can be taken before it is too late (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2012).
6. Information obtained from data analytics helps organisations segment customers based on their socioeconomic status as well as increase their levels of satisfaction.

IV. INDUSTRY 4.0 AND ITS EXPECTATIONS FOR ORGANISATIONS

Industrial development has evolved into four stages of the industrial revolution. The mechanical revolution involved doing work with machines instead of working with hands or animals. The second revolution is the stage of the mass production era. It was the application of technology to increase the production of large amounts of similar products with little human effort. The third stage of the industrial revolution was the development of digital computers to enhance connectivity and access to trade and public services.

The fourth industrial revolution is the emergence of Industry 4.0. It uses technologies such as data analytics and the Internet of Things to monitor the production process (Singhal, 2021). Industry 4.0, also called a smart factory, is the act of using computers in the manufacturing process (computer-aided manufacturing) to take charge of the whole production process in the industry (Rai et al., 2021; Sadiku et al., 2022). Industry 4.0 focuses on connectivity, intelligence and flexible automation (Machado et al., 2020; Rai et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021). Manufacturing was defined as the coupling of components into finished products on a large scale to produce high-quality products at minimised cost (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2023).

Industry 4.0 is based on intelligent systems with Internet of Things and Internet of Services (Haller et al., 2009; Hogan et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2022) and big data mining (Oks et al., 2017; Oliff & Liu, 2017). Industry 4.0 offers industries the possibilities of digital transformation and data-driven solutions through the application of big data analytics and data analysis tools (Elgendy & Elragal, 2014; Komal, 2018). Manufacturers can gain insights to optimise productivity through the application of data analysis.

The goal of Industry 4.0 is to use digital technology to automate the processes involved in manufacturing to maximise efficiency and identify barriers before they occur (Rai et al., 2021) and lowering production costs of existing industries and increasing product quality and innovation (Oliff & Liu, 2017; Xu et al., 2021). Industry 4.0 helps to address workforce insufficiency and promotes competence in performance (Machado et al., 2020). Industry 4.0 implies manufacturing in the industry.

Industry 4.0 connects the digital world to the physical world using computer-based algorithms, sensors and devices to link and exchange data with systems and other devices over the Internet (Gokalp et al., 2016; Rai et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021). Industry 4.0 aims at increasing individualised customer requirements (Machado et al., 2020). It is the technological evolution from embedded systems to cyber-physical systems (Gröger, 2018; Oks et al., 2017). A Cyber-physical system is the physical production steps accompanied by computer-based processes (Oks et al., 2017). Industry 4.0 is the digitalisation of the manufacturing sector and the analysis of all relevant data (Manyika et al., 2011).

V. HADOOP AND ITS COMPONENTS

Hadoop is an open-source software framework that supports the processing and storage of large amounts of data sets with high processing power and the ability to handle concurrent tasks. Hadoop provides two fundamental functions for data processing; Map and Reduce (Rajput & Mehta, 2017). Map combines and transforms the data supplied by the user while Reduce groups the output obtained from Map. Hadoop is best for handling big data processing. Hadoop processes big data in a distributed computing environment (Rajput & Mehta, 2017). Hadoop Technology process massive data in an efficient, cost-effective and timely manner (Khan et al., 2014).

Hadoop, MapReduce and Big Table are some of the most commonly used tools used for the organisation and

examination of big data. Hadoop comprises of Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS), MapReduce, HBase, Hcatalog, Pig, Hive, Oozie, Zookeeper Mahout, and Kafka. HDFS and MapReduce are the most well-known component

of Hadoop (Khan et al., 2014).

Figure 1 shows the Hadoop ecosystem. Table 1 depicts the components of Hadoop and their functions.

Figure 1: Hadoop Ecosystem (Khan et al., 2014)

Table 1: Hadoop components and their functions

Hadoop Component	Functions
HDFS	Stores large volumes of data and its fault tolerance is high.
MapReduce	Analyses complex big data.
HBASE	Increases the performance of similar data in big data.
HCatalog	Enables users with diverse processing tools into a grid with little effort.
Pig	Enables users to execute jobs in MapReduce.
Mahout	It is a collection of machine learning and data mining tools.
Oozie	Scheduling and executing workflow in Hadoop.
ZooKeeper	Maintains and coordinates large volumes of data.
Kafka	Massive message streams and data integration for data analysis
Hive	Facilities for storing data.

HDFS is used for handling big data beyond the capacity of one machine. HDFS facilitates the concurrent processing of massive data. HDFS stores a very large volume of data and its fault tolerance is very high (Rajput & Mehta, 2017). HDFS architecture is made up of three nodes which include the Name, Data and Edge nodes. The name Node plays the role of the master node, Data Node plays the role of the Slave Node and the Edge Node acts as a link between the Data node and Name node. The Name nodes receive requests from the Edge node and transfer these requests to Data nodes where successful requests will reside.

HBase: Relies entirely on the zookeeper instance to increase the performance of operations over similar values across large data sets.

HCatalog: It stores metadata and generates tabular data of HIVE metastore to enhance users with diverse data processing tools to write data into a grid without difficulty.

Pig: generates a high-level platform that creates programs (Pig latin) that enables users to execute jobs in MapReduce.

Mahout: This is a collection of machine learning and data mining tools.

Oozie: organises, executes and schedules job flow.

Avro: A data serialisation framework that provides data exchange services, between big data in any programming language. It performs remote procedure calls.

Zookeeper: provides the services of maintenance, configuration and naming of large amounts of data.

A. Advantages of the Components of Hadoop (Suguna, 2016)

1. Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) is not expensive, and the fault tolerance is high.
2. HBase is consistent and its flexibility is high.
3. Hive has infrastructure for storing data.
4. Pig saves development time and reduces duplication of data.
5. Zookeeper produces reliable data, it is simple and fast to use.
6. Mahout analyses and mines large volumes of data. It is used for data mining to find hidden patterns.
7. Oozie allows jobs to be controlled from anywhere.

VI. CHALLENGES OF BIG DATA

Despite the benefits of big data and data analytics, they face a lot of problems and challenges. A few of these challenges are discussed below.

1. Representation of data, which can result in the reduction of data validity and originality and eventually cause ineffective data analysis. A well-represented data will show data structure, class, type and integrated technologies, which will assist in efficient operations

- on the various data set and reduce redundancy and cost.
- Data contradiction and deficiency, untimeliness and scalability (Ajah & Nweke, 2019; Prarthana & Jayakumar, 2017; Raheem & Uwanthika, 2019).
- Traditional methods cannot process massive heterogeneous data within a given period.
- Data security. The major risk in big data is data insecurity (Khan et al., 2014). A situation where data is constantly being attacked by unauthorised persons and data confidentiality is not guaranteed.
- Lack of supervision of electrical energy consumed during the Processing, transmission and storage of big data.

A. Solutions to Big Data Challenges

Some of the solutions to these challenges stated above can be handled by cloud computing since it can accommodate large data computing and data storage.

- Hadoop manages big data by effectively processing large amounts of data at an effectively reduced cost promptly (Khan et al., 2014).
- Distributed storage systems that are consistent, available and partitioned tolerance, and have the ability of tolerating problems caused by network failure should be used for big data storage (Khan et al., 2014).
- Ensure data integrity by preventing illegal and unauthorised tampering of data and data usage. It has to do with the quality and reliability of data.
- Encryption of large amounts can also be a form of preservation of privacy and security.
- Data security policies should be put in place to checkmate people and security agents from using data generated by people without permission.
- Expandability and scalability. The system that is developed for data analytics should support both the present and future data sets. Also, the algorithms must be able to analyse ever more large and complex data sets.
- The establishment of a comprehensive big data network architecture may be necessary to provide access to scientists from various fields so that the analytical objectives could be achieved.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper discussed big data and the benefits that are realised from the analysis of big data using data analytics. Data analytics are advanced analytical techniques applied to big data to extract patterns and information to help business organisations understand their business trends and make quick decisions. Further, the paper discussed Industry 4.0, also called the smart factory, whose goal is to use digital technology to connect to the physical world to maximise efficiency, lower production costs and increase product quality in the industry. Industry 4.0 is the digitalisation of the manufacturing sector and the analysis of relevant data. It also discussed big data challenges and proffered some solutions to these challenges. Hadoop and its components cannot address all the problems of big data, and SAS, R and MATLAB are not suitable. Proper tools for analysis are still lacking.

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